

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FREQUENCY AND MICROBIOLOGICAL PROFILE OF
REPRODUCTIVE TRACT INFECTIONS IN USERS OF INTRA-
UTERINE DEVICES**¹Dr. Maria Zafar, ²Dr. Soofia Zafar Qadri, ³Dr. Farah Zafar Qadri¹Rawalpindi Medical College, Rawalpindi,²WAH Medical College³Central Park Medical College.**Abstract**

Objective: To determine the frequency and etiological agents responsible for reproductive tract infections in women using intra-uterine devices as a mode of contraception.

Study Design: Descriptive study.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was conducted at the Department Of Pathology ,and Obstet .& Gynae Rawalpindi Medical College from April 2016_june 2017.

Materials and Methods: Total of 203 female patients who have chosen IUD as a method of contraception were included in the study. High vaginal and endocervical swabs were taken and sent for microbiological analysis from patients who presented with clinical features of reproductive tract infection.

Results: Mean age of study participants was 32.61 ± 5.49 years and mean duration of the next visit after IUD insertion was 24.30 ± 6.90 days. Sixty patients presented with RTI and 32 of these patients presented within three weeks of insertion of IUDs. The incidence of RTIs was 29.56% and commonest isolates were *Ureaplasmaurealyticum*, *Escherichia coli* and *Gardnerellavaginalis*.

Conclusion: All women who opt for IUD as a mode of contraception must be screened for *Ureaplasmaurealyticum* and other microbes prior to IUD insertion to avoid infections by these organisms later. Longitudinal studies with longer follow up periods should be conducted to accurately determine the frequency of RTIs as well as microbiological agents responsible for these infections.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Maria Zafar,**

Rawalpindi Medical College.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Maria Zafar et al., *Frequency And Microbiological Profile Of Reproductive Tract Infections In Users Of Intra-Uterine Devices.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Reproductive tract infections (RTIs) are characterized by the infection of genital or reproductive tract in sexually active women of reproductive age group [1]. They are ranked fifth among infectious diseases as a cause of soliciting medical care among adults and about 1/3rd of these infections occur in people of less than 25 years of age worldwide [2]. A patient suffering from RTI can present with different symptoms i.e. itching, vaginal discharge, genital ulcers, backache etc [1]. There are numerous risk factors which predispose women of reproductive age to acquire RTIs. These risk factors include menstruation, vaginal contraceptives, pregnancy and child-birth [3].

Intrauterine devices (IUDs) are commonly used and preferred mode of contraception with a prevalence rate of 15% [4]. They offer long-term contraception and they are also cost effective and well-tolerated [5,6]. IUDs are being used by more than 80 million women globally as a mode of contraception and their efficacy parallels that of tubal sterilization [6,7]. But, they have not gained much popularity in certain geographical areas due to the anticipated risk of pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) which in turn can lead to various complications e.g. ectopic pregnancy and infertility. It is believed that presence of IUD in uterine cavity predisposes host to infections and thus, PID [7]. Hence, placement and presence of IUD may lead to bacterial contamination of endometrial cavity which in turn leads to PID.

This study is carried out with the aim of determining the rate of RTIs as well as the etiological agents responsible for RTIs among females using IUD as a contraceptive method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was conducted at the Department of Pathology, and Obstet&Gynae ward Rawalpindi Medical College from April 2016 _ june 2017.

All patients between the ages of 18 – 50 years and who preferred IUD as a contraceptive method were included in the study. Women who were pregnant and who had anatomical gynecological defects as well as gynecological malignancies were excluded from the study.

About 203 patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were included in the study. IUD was inserted using sterile technique. Afterwards, patients were advised to report back immediately in case of

lower abdominal pain, vaginal spotting and discharge. In patients suspected of RTIs, high vaginal and endocervical swabs were taken and sent for microbiological examination. Bacterial isolates were identified using standard laboratory techniques [8].

Data was stored and processed using SPSS version 21. Chi square test, with p value of less than 5 taken as significant, was used to study the relationship among different variables.

RESULTS:

The mean age of 203 study participants was 32.61±5.49 years (range: 24 – 42 years). Mean duration of the next visit after IUD insertion was 24.30±6.90 days (range: 12 – 35 days).

60 patients, (29.56%), were found with genital tract infection, Table 1.

Table No. 1. Genital tract infections in study participants, (n=203)

Genital Tract Infection	Number	Percentage
Present	60	29.56%
Absent	143	70.44%
Total	203	100%

Table No. 2. Stratification of RTIs according to age and duration after insertion of IUD, (n=60)

Duration of IUD insertion	Genital tract infection		P value
	Present	Absent	
≤ 21 days	32	40	0.001*
22 - 42 days	28	103	
Total	60	143	
Age of patients			
24 – 33 years	34	73	0.46
34 – 43 years	26	70	
Total	60	143	

* P-value < 0.05

It was observed that most of genital infections were observed in younger patients between the ages of 24 – 33 years and the patients who developed these infections presented usually in first three weeks of IUD insertion, Table 2.

Majority of patients, 20 (9.85%), were suffering from Ureaplasmaurealyticum infection followed by Escherichia coli infection in 16 (7.88%) patients. Whereas each of Gardnerell-avaginalis and Neisseria gonorrhoeae were responsible for infection in 8 (3.94%) patients each, Table 3.

Table No. 3. Micro-organisms responsible for RTIs, (n=60)

Causative organism	Number of patients	%age
Ureaplasmaurealyticum	20	9.85%
Escherichia coli	16	7.88%
Neisseria gonorrhoeae	08	3.94%
Gardnerellavaginalis	08	3.94%
Mycoplasma hominis	04	1.97%
Chlamydia trachomatis	04	1.97%
Total	60	29.55%

DISCUSSION:

Reproductive tract infections pose a significant public health threat and are second most common reason for healthy life loss among females of reproductive age group in developing countries [9]. It is estimated that more than 200 million women suffer from RTIs each year in developing countries [10]. RTIs occurring secondary to contraceptives lead to ectopic pregnancy, infertility and pelvic inflammatory disease which in turn lead to higher morbidity and mortality in mothers and their neonates [8]. There is a significant loss of economic productivity secondary to morbidity related to RTIs [9].

Sixty patients, (29.56%), were diagnosed with RTIs in this study. Most of the patients, 56.67%, who were suffering from RTIs were between the ages of 24 – 33 years. Similar to our study, Ferraz et al have reported the prevalence of these infections to be 29.1% among their Brazilian patients [11]. Likewise, Egbe et al have found that the frequency of RTIs was 36.90% among their Nigerian subjects while majority of their patients, (68.18%), were between the ages of 26 – 30 years [8]. In another study conducted in Turkey by Deveer et al, the rate of RTIs was reported to be 55.9% [5]. The difference in reported rate of RTIs among different studies could be due to the variation in the rate and acceptability of IUD as a contraceptive method in different countries. Majority of our patients, 53.33%, suffering from RTIs presented within first three weeks after insertion of IUD. It is also reported that there is a higher risk of developing RTIs by the use of contraceptives especially IUDs within first few weeks 6, 12.

Ureaplasmaurealyticum was the most common isolate found in our patients followed by Escherichia coli and Neisseria gonorrhoeae. Deveer et al have found that the most common isolate was Ureaplasmaurealyticum followed by Mycoplasma hominis and Escherichia coli in their study [5].

Likewise, Kaliterna et al have reported that the most common isolates among IUD users were Ureaplasmaurealyticum and Escherichia coli in their Croatian subjects [13]. The higher incidence of Ureaplasmaurealyticum may be due to the fact that these micro-organisms are part of normal flora of female genital tract and therefore, they reach uterine cavity by the tail of IUD while insertion of IUDs.

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence of RTIs was 29.56% with Ureaplasmaurealyticum and Escherichia coli as the most common isolates. Most of the patients presented within first three weeks after insertion of IUD. All women who opt for IUD as a mode of contraception must be screened for Ureaplasmaurealyticum and other microbes prior to IUD insertion to avoid infections by these organisms later. Longitudinal studies with longer follow up periods should be conducted to accurately determine the frequency of RTIs as well as microbiological agents responsible for these infections.

Conflict of Interest: The study has no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

- Kafle P, Bhattarai SS. Prevalence and Factors Associated with Reproductive Tract Infections in Gongolia Village, Rupandehi District, Nepal. *Advances in Public Health* 2016;2016:5.
- Prasad JH, Abraham S, Kurz KM, George V, Lalitha MK, John R, et al. Reproductive tract infections among young married women in Tamil Nadu, India. *Int family planning perspectives* 2005;31(2):73-82.
- Mani G. Prevalence of reproductive tract infections among rural married women in Tamil Nadu, India: A community based study. *J Pioneer Med Sci* 2014;4(1):18-24.
- Thonneau P, Goulard H, Goyaux N. Risk factors for intrauterine device failure: a review. *Contraception* 2001;64(1):33-7.
- Deveer R, Deveer M, Sozen H, Ye Ü, Eren A, Beydilli H, et al. Infection frequency among intrauterine copper T-380A contraceptive users. *Acta Medica* 2013;29:489.
- Pal Z, Urban E, Dosa E, Pal A, Nagy E. Biofilm formation on intrauterine devices in relation to duration of use. *J Med Microbiol* 2005;54 (Pt 12):1199-203.
- Peterson HB, Xia Z, Hughes JM, Wilcox LS, Tylor LR, Trussell J. The risk of pregnancy after tubal sterilization: findings from the

- U.S. Collaborative Review of Sterilization. *Am J Obstetrics and Gynecol* 1996;174(4):1161-8; discussion 8-70.
8. Egbe CA, Onwufor UC, Omoregie R, Enabulele OI. Female Reproductive Tract Infections Among Vaginal Contraceptive Users in Benin City, Nigeria. *Genomic Medicine, Biomarkers, and Health Sciences* 2011;3(1):49-52.
 9. Elahee SMA, Mahmud S, Tanvir S, Rahman MZ. Breaking the Silence: Reproductive Tract Infections (RTIs) Among Women in Slums of Khulna City, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh e-J Sociol* 2013;10(2):119-34.
 10. World Health Organization, Global Prevalence and Incidence of Selected Transmitted Infection, Overview and Estimate, WHO, Geneva, Switzerland, 2001.
 11. Ferraz do Lago R, Simoes JA, Bahamondes L, Camargo RP, Perrotti M, Monteiro I. Follow-up of users of intrauterine device with and without bacterial vaginosis and other cervicovaginal infections. *Contraception* 2003;68(2):105-9.
 12. Sowmini C, Sankara S. Reproductive morbidity among contraceptive users: need for quality services. *J Family Welfare* 2004;50(1):31-7.
 13. Kaliterna V, Kucisec-Tepes N, Pejkoivic L, Zavorovic S, Petrovic S, Barisic Z. An intrauterine device as a possible cause of change in the microbial flora of the female genital system. *J Obstet Gynaecol Res* 2011;37(8):1035-40.
 14. Viscardi RM. Ureaplasma species: role in diseases of prematurity. *Clinics in Perinatol* 2010;37(2): 393-409.